

Q. What is Vocabulary Control?

Ans. 'Vocabulary Control' is a list of standardized terms, chosen and organized by trained professionals, who possess expertise in the subject area. It provides the subject of every document. VC is one of the most important components of an IRS. Libraries and Information Centres uses VC for indexing and retrieve information.

Lancaster identifies two principal objectives of Vocabulary Control within an information retrieval environment:

1. to promote the consistent representation of subject matter by indexers and searchers, thereby avoiding the dispersion of related materials. This is achieved through the control(merging) of synonymous and nearly synonymous expressions and by distinguishing among homographs
2. to facilitate the conduct of a comprehensive search on some topic by linking together terms whose meaning are related paradigmatically or syntagmatically.

Q. What is the need of Controlled Vocabulary in IR?

Ans. Effectiveness of Information Retrieval System depends on two things- recall and precision. Controlled vocabulary helps IRS in performing these things.

Recall can be improved through VC- controlled vocabularies generally employed by human indexers. These vocabularies are uniquely designed for the individuals (indexers) who utilize them. Human indexers do not include every crucial word in a document, as a computer might; however, they attempt to identify the main subjects and assign controlled terms to represent those. This process aids users in finding relevant documents, although it may not be comprehensive.

CV enhances search precision by eliminating irrelevant noise in the search results. When users search for information using standardized terms, the system matches those terms within the indexed content. This not only saves time for users and service providers, but it also improves the overall efficiency of IRS.

Q. What are the tools of Vocabulary Control?

Ans. 1. Subject Headings Lists

A vocabulary control device relies on a master list of terms (which can be assigned to various documents). This master list of terms is referred to as the 'List

of Subject Headings.' A list of subject headings contains the subject access terms that are preferred for use in the cataloguing or indexing operation.

Example- Sears list of subject headings

Library of Congress Subject Headings

2. Thesauri

The traditional definition of a thesaurus refers to a type of dictionary that incorporates synonyms or alternative expressions for every term. Moreover, it may also include antonyms. The Oxford English Dictionary defines the term 'thesaurus' (an archaeological concept) as "a treasury of temple, etc.," and it cites its usage in 1736 as a treasury or storehouse of knowledge.

A dictionary lists words along with their meanings, synonyms, etc. in alphabetical order, but a thesaurus assembles all words related to an idea at one place.

3. Thesaurofacet

Thesaurofacet represents a distinct form of retrieval language, encompassing both a thesaurus-like and a classification-oriented display. Each of these components contains certain terms that are unique to itself; these terms are not present in the other.

4. Classaurus

Classaurus is a vocabulary control tool developed by Ganesh Bhattacharya at Documentation Research and Training Centre (DRTC).

Q. What is Classaurus?

Ans. Classaurus is a vocabulary control tool developed by Ganesh Bhattacharya at Documentation Research and Training Centre (DRTC).

It has two parts-

The Systematic Part- consists of each entry 's Definition/scope note (whenever needed), synonyms (UF).

The Alphabetical Index Part- contains each and every term including synonyms occurring in the Systematic Part along with its address (alphanumeric code)

Q. What are the difference between Natural Language and Artificial Language?

Ans. 1. A Natural language is developed naturally in a human community by a process of use, repetition and change.

An Artificial language is deliberately created by a single creator.

2. A Natural language is developed for communication of ideas among human beings in their day- to- day life.

An Artificial language is created for specific purposes like programming, research etc.

3. A Natural language is ‘natural’ in the sense that it grows freely in the lips of human being, totally free from any control.

An Artificial language is ‘artificial’ in the sense that it is deliberately created and it is controlled.

4. A Natural language is full of homonyms, synonyms, slangs.

But an Artificial language is not that flexible.

REFERENCES

<https://www.egyankosh.ac.in/bitstream/123456789/33118/1/Unit-15.pdf>

Chowdhury, G.G. (2004). Introduction to Modern Information Retrieval. (2nd ed.). London: Facet Publishing